

Supplement to the paper “Regulatory Requirements Engineering in Large Enterprises: An Interview Study on the European Accessibility Act”

The list of the questions used during the interviews (the list does not include additional and clarifying questions that were asked when required in each particular case)

General questions about the RIA process:

- Does your enterprise have an established regulatory impact assessment process?
- What is the goal of the process?
- Who are the participants?
- What are the activities executed in the process?

The questions about each activity of the process included the following basic questions:

- What is the goal of the activity?
- What are the roles involved and who are the stakeholders of the activity?
- What are the artifacts which are used as inputs into the activity?
- What are the knowledge and expertise which are required to perform the activity?
- What are the artifacts which are an output of the activity?
- What are the challenges that you have encountered?